

PBL to design a Gamified Financial Management Application for the socially vulnerable

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Abstract

This paper presents the prototype of "MobEdu": a gamified app that responds to the need for financial management training, for a community in state of vulnerability in Brazil, with low schooling and semi-literacy, by using engagement strategies. This work was developed in partnership with five different courses conducted via Problem-Based Learning (PBL) methodology, in the Industrial Engineering course of the University of Brasília. The results presented here were obtained by students of the Production Systems Project 2 (PSP2) course, who developed exploratory research, with a qualitative approach, using FIGMA as a prototype design tool. The steps of the research were: requirements elicitation, development of a system vision document, user flow mapping and use case diagrams, and finally a prototype interface. Gamification strategies can be key elements to engage people to use an app, and this proposal was developed to promote a high engagement of the vulnerable community in a financial management application.

Keywords: Mobile Learning, Gamification, Financial Education, Interface Development, Interdisciplinary Project.

1 Introduction

In January 2018, the largest dumpsite in Latin America shut down its activities, submitting more than 1,800 waste pickers to a compensatory monthly salary payment flow of garbage cooperatives. The waste pickers community was working autonomously before, and now they have been subjected to this new mode of payment, without prior knowledge of basic financial management. In this context, researchers of the University of Brasília identified an opportunity to develop a financial management tool, aimed at communities in a state of vulnerability, with low education and semi-illiterates.

According to Vieira, Moreira Junior and Potrich (2019), Brazil's financial education is being highlighted due to the *Estratégia Nacional de Educação Financeira (ENEF)*, a national strategy that promotes financial education and social security, contributing to the strengthening of citizenship and conscious decision-making by costumers (BRASIL, 2010), developed by the Central Bank of Brazil. This was brought to practice together with another trend in education: gamification. It can be done via a strategy to make people and their organizations interact with background content and information needed for decision-making, by playing a ludic game that makes learning a challenging and funny experience (FADEL, 2014).

In addition to the development of the tool's interface, it has been noticed that challenge-based gamification improves the outcome of learning (Legaki, 2020), therefore, the format of engagement became as essential as the user interface. As a result, the application was incremented with a gamified journey, aiming at the greater engagement of the target audience in the usage of the tool's features.

This paper focuses on the results of the Production System Project 2 (PSP2) course, which has delivered a prototype of an app, and it is presented in four topics: i) theoretical references, with a theoretical basis; ii) methodology used to create the application, which unifies mobile education, financial education, and gamification; iii) results and iv) conclusions.

2 Theoretical References

A literature review was conducted to show an overview of the subject matter, and to understand the state of the art and how it could relate to the objective of this research.

This project was developed in the context of the New Epic - SDG Challenge⁸, a program that takes place every year, coordinated by a group of professors and students from the University of Aalborg, Denmark, and the University of Brasilia, Brazil. According to the UN (United Nations), the SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals) are the main focus of the 2030 Agenda, united into 17 goals, each goal represents main activities that should be considered for the achievement of the 2030 Agenda's purpose: guarantee human development and the basic needs of the citizen of the whole world through an economic, political and social process that respects the environment and sustainability in the present and the future. The projects were developed in accordance with one of those goals.

This paper presents the project "Mobile Education," related to target 2 of SDG 10 – Reduced Inequalities - "By 2030, empower and promote the social, economic and political inclusion of all, irrespective of age, sex, disability, race, ethnicity, origin, religion or economic or another status". To promote empowerment and social and economic inclusion, it is necessary to teach waste pickers how to manage their money correctly.

This project was developed in the realm of interdisciplinary projects. Interdisciplinary can be understood as the crossing of existing disciplines resulting in a new one, especially in the scientific courses in the organizational and the industrial subject fields. This is the case of Operational Research, which is an operational investigation area that came across out of the fusion among scientists, engineers, and the military (Pombo, 2008). Interdisciplinary projects are the result of the fusion of project ideas that float around in different areas, that when brought together to develop a solution, can be mutually beneficial in finding methods and tools to achieve their goals. Interdisciplinary projects are a trend in modern education and university courses are being designed to meet this goal: to bring students and professors of different knowledge areas or courses working together, in learning by doing manner. The work in an environment that is project-based education and solution-driven initiatives, with cooperation in many different levels (EVANGELISTA; COLARES; FERREIRA, 2009).

Bayuk (2019) presents how smartphone apps can aid in the financial health of their end-users. The study was conducted in an interdisciplinary manner, by exposing the group under review to game apps about finance that has social tools, such as abilities to share achievements, or economic tools, such as the ability to earn real money. The study found that consumers vary in their preferences for certain features based on their previous experiences with other financial management apps, with those who had prior contact tending to exhibit greater subjective knowledge and engage more with "social" and "economic" features of financial apps, while those with no experience are more motivated by economic features.

Vieira, Bataglia and Sereia (2011) define financial education as measures that aim to create and transmit financial information to individuals, by providing them the ability to distinguish the advantages and risks of their choices. Moraes (2019) explains that the main objective of financial education is to instruct people on how to manage their monetary resources, by helping them make conscious decisions that enable them to save and invest, and ensuring that they live well financially, whether in the present or the future.

According to Legaki et al. (2020), challenge-based gamification improves learning outcomes. As a result, it showed that the performance of their study audience was improved by 34% through gamified education and that better results can be acquired through gamification combined with traditional study methods such as reading. However, any interaction with a gamified application, in a lecture, for example, can already be considered beneficial to students. Peixoto et al. (2015) present in his study a systematic mapping of the use of gamification in educational software in the context of Brazilian research and concluded that only thirteen Brazilian institutions conduct studies in the field of gamification for education, and the software most used are web-based systems.

3 Methods used

This paper is an outcome of a project developed under the Mega-theme "Mobile Education" of the SDG Challenge. It involved five different courses from Production Engineering PSPs courses (i.e., Production Systems

⁸ The mission of the SDG-Challenge is to connect and mobilize students and organisations to work together on the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the United Nations (UN). These goals are set to combat climate change and to reduce the inequalities in the world. [New EPIC + SDG Challenge 2020. https://www.sdgchallenge.com.br/](https://www.sdgchallenge.com.br/)

Projects) of the University of Brasilia (UnB): Production Systems Project 1, 2, 3, 5 and 8 (PSP1, PSP2, PSP3, PSP5 and PSP8), in an interdisciplinary manner. PSP1 carried out the data collection via interviews, thus supporting the Production System Project 2 (PSP2) course in the requirements elicitation with stakeholders. PSP2 students were responsible for the design of a prototype interface. PSP3 teams created the educational content that is displayed in the application. PSP5 teams worked on the quality control of the prototype developed by PSP2, and the PSP8 team managed the integration of the project portfolio, all those five courses were managed by using PBL (Problem Based Learning) as a learning methodology.

The app's interface was developed with a focus on a challenge-based gamification journey, to engage and motivate the target users of the platform, based on the DML (Dynamic Model for Gamification in Learning), presented by Peixoto and Silva (2015) and Kim (2013).

The focus of this research was the PSP2 course, responsible for the development of the app prototype named "MobEdu". An applied research was carried out, with a qualitative approach, and the techniques used for data collection were based on querying an indexed database for requirements elicitation, in addition to the input provided by the PSP1 course.

The research methodology was structured in 5 phases: (i) Development of a system vision document, (ii) Requirements Elicitation, (iii) User Flow Mapping, (iv) Use Case Diagrams and (v) Prototype Interface.

4 Research Results

4.1 System Vision Document

A vision document was written by the PSP2 group in order to provide a high-level system view and more detailed technical requirements of the application, such as scope and non-scope, app building team, functional and non-functional requirements (represented visually in Figure 2), constraints, and a primary interface prototype.

The vision document was essential to present to the stakeholders (professors and students) the steps taken to elicit the functional and non-functional requirements via user's needs and a literature review, to meet the expectations, to adapt them to stakeholders' suggestions, such as in the application's boundaries and the interfaces, to build the application's prototype.

4.2 Requirements Elicitation

The system requirements specification was divided in two parts, based on Pressman (2009): the functional requirements, which refer to all the features that the application must present, described in Table 1, and the non-functional requirements, which refer to the services and restrictions presented by the system, described in Table 2.

Table 1. System Functional requirements list.

N°	Name	Functional Requirements Description.
RF001	Register and log in	It allows performing user registration by storing information, user and password.
RF002	User Validation	It allows to view and validate information about application users.
RF003	Change User	It allows to view, change and delete information about application users.
RF004	Create Avatar	It allows the creation a user's avatar.
RF005	Edit Avatar	It allows to view and edits the user's avatar
RF006	Store Avatar	It allows the storage and view of accessories purchased with fictional coins.
RF007	Control fictional coins.	It allows to record and view historical earnings and spending of fictional coins.
RF008	Include Courses	It allows you to insert courses into the app.
RF009	Keep Courses	It allows changing existing courses in the app, as well as recording and viewing completed courses.
RF010	Exclude Courses	It allows deleting existing courses in the app.
RF011	Integrate family users	It allows to create, change and delete a family group.

RF012	Integrate work users	It allows to create, change and delete workgroups.
RF013	Keep financial control	It allows to record, change, view and delete financial data.
RF014	Share link	It allows sharing the application link with a certain personalized identifier for each user so that you benefit only.
RF015	User Guide	It allows solving app usability questions.
RF016	Control Notifications	It allows controlling notifications for everyday alerts and fosters user engagement

Table 2. Non-functional requirements list.

N°	Name	Non-functional Requirements Description
RNF001	Usability	The system must make it easy for the user to understand the functionality available by using symbols. It should have a simple presentation making the execution of actions intuitive and logical.
RNF002	Performance	The system must have a maximum response time of 3 seconds.
RNF003	Storage	The system must be able to store data both locally and in the cloud.
RNF004	Security	The system must be able to register a password per user.
RNF005	Compatibility	Must be compatible with Android 6.0 or higher operational systems.
RNF006	Legality	The system must comply with the General Data Protection Law (LGPD) as well as restrictions for an application by entering the terms of use, terms of the customer.

4.3 User Flow Mapping

The user flow mapping shows the main features that users need order to use the app. It was built according to the system requirements specifications and shows the required user journey in order to achieve the functions related to the financial education goals.

Figure 1. User Flow Map

Initially, the user opens the application, to log in or to create a new account. Then user must enter their main data, create their avatar and search through their contact list to find other users in the app. Then the user is directed to Home page of the application, and has the view of four main icons on the dashbar: Wallet, Plus, Teams and Profile. In addition, the user can also navigate through the homepage and access other relevant information such as: courses, medals, coins, etc

4.4 Use-case Diagram

The use case diagram, shown in Figure 2, was designed out the list of the functional requirements, presented in section 3.2, and by analysing the business model.

The use-case diagram represents the interaction between the user and the system administrator, and their main assignments within the application.

Figure 2. Use-case diagram.

4.5 Prototype Interface

The application was created to help waste pickers to take better care of their finances. The scenarios presented in the application's prototype bring features and elements designed exclusively to better meet the needs of those users, in total, 69 interfaces were created, however, only 22 will be presented below.

The designing and prototyping of the application, throughout the research, were created by using the following tools: "Figma" - used to effectively design the screens and visualize them as a functional application; "Power BI" – Used for testing the application's points and data entry system by displaying reports; "Adobe Illustrator" – Used for designing the application-specific content; and "Miro" – used for the collaborative work of the prototype development team, of a flowchart of the app's screens.

4.5.1 Registration and Login

The Welcome screen was built to guide the user during the registration process in the application and to collect key data, such as name, phone number, and identification number. After registering, it is possible to accept the option to find friends and family who use the application. The user can also choose to indicate friends and family by sending a link, from the moment the link is used, the main user obtains their first virtual coins. On the Login screen, the user should fill in their identification number and password to enter the account. In the case of forgetting the password, the user should choose the "forgot my password" button, receiving a confirmation code by message to set a new password.

Figure 3.a Welcome, 3.b Login, 3.c Reward Pop-up

4.5.2 Creating an Avatar

In Figure 4, the user can create their avatar by choosing the skin tone, hairstyle and clothing pieces for the top and bottom parts. When creating the avatar, the user is rewarded with virtual coins to spend on accessories in the app store.

Figure 4.a Avatar creation, 4.b Avatar creation, 4.b Store, 4.c Reward Pop-up

4.5.3 Home page features

Figure 5. a presents the home screen, the screen offers the user an overview of the main information available in the app, it presents monthly earnings and expenses, progress in the financial education courses, earned coins (Figure 6.a), courses (Figure 6.b), medals (Figure 6.c) and store (Figure 4.c). Figure 5.b, presents the navigation bar, where the user can navigate through other screens, such as the wallet (Figure 8.a), the team's screen (Figure 9.a), and the profile configuration screen (Figure 7.a).

Figure 5.a Home, 5.b Overview

4.5.4 Courses and Medals

Figure 6.a presents how the coins were obtained, after the registration, virtual coins can be obtained through three steps: by indication, by adding data to the earnings or expenses report, or by watching the available courses in the app. Figure 6.b presents the courses screen, where the user can access the financial education content of the application. Figure 6.c presents the medals earned by finished courses, the user also has the

option to share the medal via WhatsApp (Figure 6.d), medals with a lock symbol can be obtained by completing the equivalent course.

Figure 6.a Calendar, 6.b Courses, 6.c Medals Overview, 6.d Share your Medal

4.5.5 User's profile features

Figure 7.a presents the registered user information. Figure 7.b presents frequently asked questions and instructions for the app usage. Figure 7.c presents the settings option of the app: privacy, notifications, change password, invite code, search contacts, term of the user and deactivate the account.

Figure 7.a Profile, 7.b Help, 7.c Settings

4.5.6 Financial Information

By clicking on the button with the plus symbol on the home page "+", it is possible to add the expenses and earnings data of the day (Figure 8.a). The "General" screen shows the available income, the average weekly expenditure, and the expected expense for the month (Figure 8.b). Users can delete the financial records (Figure 8.d) by clicking on the pencil and notebook icon in the upper left corner of the dashboard (Figure 8.c). The dashboard is divided into "Earnings" and "Expenses" and has a table with the date, value and reason for the expense (Figure 8.d). The user can also listen to the dashboard analysis by clicking on the speaker located in the upper right corner (Figure 8d).

Figure 8.a Financial Input, 8.b General, 8.c Delete Information, 8.c Dashboard

4.5.7 Family and Work Team

The Family and Work Team strategy is responsible for the integration between users. In this section, it is possible to create teams and have visibility of the number of coins of each player.

Figure 9. Work Team

5 Conclusions

This project resulted in the prototyping of a gamified app that helps socially vulnerable communities develop critical thinking and financial management abilities through financial management courses and tool that are made available by the application. Those results were accomplished due to the integration between five problem-based learning (PBL) classes of Production System Project (PSP) of the Production Engineering course of the University of Brasília, whose students worked together to design a solution to participate in the Epic and SDG Challenge, which is a program that takes place every year, coordinated by a group of professors and students from the University of Aalborg, Denmark, and the University of Brasília, Brazil.

Besides the main objective, the project also had the purpose of developing students skills through problem-based learning (PBL) and multidisciplinary critical thinking. Those goals were achieved through the integration

of courses that applied knowledge about project management, quality management, requirements elicitation and product development.

The project was developed based on real needs, in addition to developing a solution to a latent social problem in Brazil, the lack of training on financial management of communities in a state of vulnerability. Students at the University of Brasília had the opportunity to develop their autonomy and creativity, in addition to applying theoretical knowledge learned in the classroom, in a solution that brings value to Brazilian society and cooperates with the strategic objectives of the UN 2030 Agenda.

Due to the social isolation imposed because of the COVID-19 pandemic, the project did not have a validation phase with the target audience, waste pickers from the SLU. As a next step, the study will continue with a hands-on real user experience with waste pickers to validate the application outcome and improve the project's results.

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